

Impact of Science and Technology Research in Federal University Otuoke Community, Nigeria

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Abstract

The role of science and technology in societal progress has been a recurring discussion topic at various academic conferences. There is widespread concern about Nigeria's readiness for the digital development economy. The researchers in Science and Technology at Federal University Otuoke, Nigeria, were studied using a hybrid methodology that included quantitative and qualitative content analysis of their Google Scholar profiles. The findings demonstrate a substantial link between the number of publications and the amount of citations/impact. This association is supported further by the number of community projects undertaken by high-ranking researchers in Chemistry, Microbiology, Chemical Engineering, and Library and Information Science. While recommending that government increase financing for relevant science and technology research in order to improve community development in Nigeria.

Keywords: Science and Technology, Research, Community, Federal University Otuoke, Nigeria

Research Sponsored by 2021 TetFund IBR Intervention through Federal University Otuoke

Introduction

Nigeria, the most populous nation in Africa with over 200 million citizens (Kamer, 2023) has the human resources to compete with China and India as a top nation in science and technology as well as in research and development. However, the nation is falling behind the rest of the world significantly. However, the lack of visible scientific and technology research and the insufficiency of science and technology have significantly hampered Nigeria's progress as a nation. If only individuals from the older age are tackling crucial issues surrounding research and innovation for the nation, it raises questions about whether Nigeria is genuinely prepared for the digital economy. The examination and bibliographic analysis of scientific and technological research holds the secret to Nigeria's and any other nation's present and future development. The concepts will assist researchers and all other stakeholders in identifying a research discipline's productivity through the number of papers it publishes. The frequency with which a published work is cited in subsequent publications is also regarded as a sign of the level of interest in the topic and the calibre of the paper. Through proper access to relevant research, these elements play a crucial part in the wealth enhancement of life quality as well as true economic growth and transformation in every

community. In essence, technology is the primary driver of economic progress. It is the most important and essential necessity for adding value to raw materials and people. It is the key to unlocking a country's potential in terms of lowering overhead expenses connected with outsourcing and providing job possibilities. The purpose of this study is to identify, collect, and analyse research output in Science and Technology from Federal University Otuoke in Bayelsa State, South-South Nigeria, as well as to analyse the impact on the Federal University Otuoke community. The overarching goal is to considerably increase the institution's research productivity as well as the state's and Nigeria's technological growth.

Research Question:

1. What is the impact of Science and Technology Research in the Federal University Otuoke Community?

Related Literature on Science and Technology Research Impact

Alan and Ananda (2018) used a qualitative method with a descriptive approach to see the technology in the midst of society to examine Technology Development and its impact on community social behaviour. They noticed that the presence of technology was inextricably linked to human users, and that society is becoming increasingly reliant on technology. Anaeto et al. (2016) also investigated the importance of science and technology in national development. According to the report, the divide between rich and poor countries is mostly due to technological gaps and the difficulty in applying them to societal problems.

Djeki, Degila, Bondiombouy, and Alhassan (2022), in their paper titled "E-learning bibliometric analysis from 2015 to 2020," tried to perform a complete examination of the e-learning research field by conducting a bibliometric analysis of 12,272 publications from the Web of Science database between 2015 and 2020. The study's goals were to highlight collaborations between authors, universities, and countries in the field, to identify the most influential authors, universities, countries, and reference papers, to learn about the research topics on which researchers have been working in recent years, and to investigate African contributions in the field. According to the statistics, the United States, Spain, England, and China were the most productive countries in terms of e-learning. A very prominent author Tarhini, on eLearning researchers states that host Universities are primarily from the United Kingdom, the United States, and China. The most represented journals were Computers in Human Behaviour, Computers & Education, and International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning; the most influential universities were Islamic Azad University, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, and King Abdulaziz University. The investigation revealed that there was little collaboration among authors, universities, and countries working on e-learning, and that COVID-19 had a substantial impact on e-learning. Africans' contributions and research on e-learning and its security were demonstrated to be inadequate.

Another study, titled "Bibliometric Analysis of Research Assessing the Use of Acupuncture for Pain Treatment over the Last 20 Years," was conducted by Lee, Lee, Chen, and Chae (2020). The study

used a bibliometric approach with quantitative analytical tools to investigate the evolution of research into acupuncture for the treatment of pain. A visualisation analysis of journal articles was also used in this study to assess the present state of acupuncture analgesia. The Web of Science database was utilised to obtain data for the study, which focused on articles on acupuncture for pain control published between 2000 and 2019. The extracted records were examined in terms of publication year, nation, journal, research area, authors, and organisational affiliations. The VOS viewer programme was used to visualise trends in pain control research. The total number of publications has steadily increased over the previous 20 years, according on analyses of 4595 original and review articles. The United States produced the most articles in this field, followed by China and South Korea. A network analysis of term cooccurrence indicated three major types of studies: clinical studies, pain management studies, and mechanism investigations. The study used bibliometric approaches to evaluate research on acupuncture for pain control, revealing current trends in acupuncture analgesia research as well as prospective future hot spots of research in this subject.

Sweileh (2020) published the findings of a study titled "Bibliometric analysis of peer-reviewed literature on climate change and human health with an emphasis on infectious diseases." The study concluded that research is critical for developing future protective and adaptive strategies. The current study's goal was to examine research activities on climate change and health, with a focus on infectious diseases. SciVerse Scopus was used as a bibliometric tool. Climate change and human health materials were referred to as "health-related literature," whereas climate change and infectious diseases documents were referred to as "infection-related literature." The study lasted from 1980 to 2019. The search query turned up 4247 items in the medical literature and 1207 in the infection-related literature. After 2007, the number of publications increased dramatically. Environmental Health Perspectives journal documents obtained the most citations per document. A total of 1416 (33.3%) health-related literature documents were financed, whereas 419 (34.7%) infection-related literature publications were awarded.

A comparable study named "Bibliometric Analysis of Trends in Theory-related Policy Publications" was conducted by Zahra, Nurmandi, Tenorio, Rahayu, Benectitos, Mina, and Haictin (2021). The bibliometric analysis conducted for the study assessed the extent and trends of theory-related policy articles in major international journals. The approach identified policy-related papers by using the Scopus search engine on random journals. In addition, a data visualisation software called VOS viewer was employed in the study to analyse the outcomes, underlying network links, and information production trends in policy analysis. The data revealed that only a small minority of policy-related studies employ theories in their research. Practitioners published less research in field-specific journals than in interdisciplinary science and technology journals.

A paper titled "A Bibliometric Analysis of Online Faculty Professional Development in Higher Education" by Gao, Wong, Khambari, and Noodin (2022). The research focused on online faculty professional development (OFPD) in higher education, which they noted has risen in recent years. Given the scarcity of quantitative studies on research publications in this field, a bibliometric study of 248 papers

from the Scopus database was performed. For descriptive and network analysis, the software tools Biblioshiny and VOSviewer were utilised. According to the research findings, the overall trend of publication in this sector has increased consistently at an annual growth rate of 14.11% during the last 25 years. In terms of publication and citation numbers, the Journal of Asynchronous Learning Network and Computers and Education scored first and second, respectively. Peter Shea was named the most influential author, with 298 citations to his paper, while Maria Northcote was named the most productive, with five publications. In terms of geographical location of research activities, America led the way, with Asia emerging as a contender. Dede et al.'s work "A Research Agenda for Online Teacher Professional Development" topped the list in terms of overall citations as well as average yearly citations. In terms of current trends, teacher professional development through online instruction emerged as a result of the Covid-19 outbreak. The themes that researchers were most interested in were pedagogy training, online community building, and assisting online teachers.

In Nigeria, there have been some bibliometric studies. Salisu and Salami (2020) conducted research titled "A Bibliometric Analysis of Nigeria's Research Performance, 1901-2016." The research looked at Nigerian publications indexed in the Scopus database from 1901 to 2016. The study shed light on Nigerian research performance, publishing trends, publication patterns, and partnership patterns at both the national and international levels. A total of 95,304 publications were examined using bibliometric indicators and statistics. The findings revealed a steady increase in Nigerian publications after independence; a preference for article publications over conference papers and reviews, as well as frequent collaboration within the country versus outside the country; and that the majority of research publications in Nigeria come from universities.

Another study, titled "Infoveillance and bibliometric analysis of COVID-19 in Nigeria," was conducted by Amzat, Kanmodi, and Egbedina (2023). The purpose of this study was to examine the patterns of internet search and research interest in COVID-19 in Nigeria. This was an infoveillance and bibliometric investigation on COVID-19 in Nigeria that used a systemic search through Google Trends to gather COVID-19 information prevalence and research incidence by bibliometric analysis utilising the SCOPUS database. The acquired data were examined using Microsoft Excel 2021 programme. According to the findings, the information search increase began one week before the first index case. Inequalities in search volume index were discovered across the country, with northern Nigeria having greater search traffic for COVID-19. This survey also discovered other top search terms, such as "COVID-19," "COVID loan," and "vaccine," as well as searches such as "COVID-19 Nigeria," "COVID loan," and "COVID-19 in Nigeria," among others, indicating major 'infodemiologic' issues in Nigeria. The interests of Nigerian researchers in COVID-19 span across areas. Medicine, Social Sciences, and Biochemistry were the top three topic areas with the highest amount of these papers. This analysis discovered considerable research collaboration with more than 150 countries, as well as external funding.

Adedayo, Adio, and Oboirien's work was titled "Energy Research in Nigeria: A Bibliometric Analysis" in 2021. The study looked at Nigeria's limited energy supply in proportion to its energy demand, which sparked interest in the scientific exploration of diverse energy research. This study reports on a bibliometric examination of Nigerian scholars' energy papers from 1974 to 2019 (45 years) from the Elsevier Scopus database. The analysis includes publication kinds, language of publication, and author and collaborator institutions. According to the analysis, the number of publications has increased during the last 45 years. Significant changes occurred from 2006 to 2015, with an average of 113 publications per year decreasing to an average of 326 articles per year from 2016 to 2019. According to the contributions of institutional energy publications by region, the South-Western States region had the most publications. A global map depicted international energy partnership. Nigerian authors primarily collaborated on energy papers with institutions in South Africa, Malaysia, the United States, and the United Kingdom. The publications focused primarily on solar energy, wind energy, and biomass energy, with less emphasis on gas and hydro energy, which are Nigeria's primary sources of electricity generation. There appears to have been no evaluation of the influence of research on science and technology in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. This research endeavour is an attempt to fill that void noted from all the previous studies on this area.

Methodology

As of January 2023, Federal University Otuoke had 358 academic staff members. 170 of them work in scientific and technology research at the Faculties of Engineering, scientific, and Education. The instrument for this study was distributed to all 170 academic staff members working in science and technology research. 102 survey respondents either completed the questionnaire or provided access to their study via the ResearchGate and Google Scholar platforms. This accounts for 60% of the target population.

Table: 1 Population of S & T Researchers in FUU

S/NO	FACULTY	DEPARTMENTS	FUU STAFF IN S & T	N0 OF FUU POP in S & T
1.	Engineering	1. Chemical Engineering	12	5
		2. Civil Engineering	15	7
		3. Elect/Elect	14	6
		4. Mechanical	13	5
		5. Engineering	9	6
		6. Pet and Gas Mechatronics	10	1
2.	Science	1. Biology	7	7
		2. Biochemistry	8	5
		3. Chemistry	20	18
		4. Computer Science	14	7
		5. Microbiology	13	11
		6. Mathematics & Statistics	14	7
3.	Education	1. Science Education	9	6
		2. Library and Information	12	11

		Science		
		Total	170	102

Source. (Etim et al., 2023)

There were three research instruments. First, a Google form was evaluated and content approved by a cross-section of FUIO academic employees from Faculties that were not involved in the project. Academic staff members who have been cited in the Google Scholar database were also evaluated. Deans and heads of science and technology departments were also interviewed.

Results and Analysis

Science & Technology Publications in Federal University Otuoke

Table: 2 Number of Publications in Different Areas of Science & Technology in FUIO

S/N	Faculty	Department	N0 of FUIO Population in S & T	Number of Publications
1	Engineering	Chemical Engineering	5	184
		Civil Engineering	7	104
		Elect/Electronics	6	117
		Mechanical Engineering	5	53
		Pet and Gas	6	58
		Mechatronics	1	1
2	Science	Biology	7	124
		Biochemistry	5	170
		Chemistry	18	500
		Computer Science	7	65
		Microbiology	11	321
		Mathematics & Statistics	7	169
3	Education	Science Education	6	48
		Library and Information Science	11	210
		Total	102	2,124

Source. (Etim et al., 2023)

Department of Chemistry had the largest number of publications (500) out of the 18 faculty members evaluated. Chemistry is the study of substances, their composition, structure, and the transformations they go through. Organic chemistry, biochemistry, inorganic chemistry, analytical chemistry, and physical chemistry are the primary sub-disciplines of chemistry. Department of Microbiology returned in second with 321 articles from 11 staff members. The study of the biology of tiny

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organisms such as viruses, bacteria, algae, fungi, slime moulds, and protozoa is known as microbiology. Microbiology research includes all aspects of these microorganisms, including their behaviour, evolution, ecology, biochemistry, and physiology, as well as the pathology of diseases caused by them. Bacteriology, immunology, mycology, nematology, parasitology, phycology, protozoology, and virology are all branches of microbiology. Library and Information Science, an interdisciplinary topic of study that deals with the organisation, access, acquisition, protection/regulation of information in both physical and digital forms, the department of Library and Information Science came in third place with 210 publications from 11 staff members.

Figure 1: Graphic representation of the relationship between the Study Population and the number of publications

Source: (Etim et al., 2023)

Table: 3 Quantitative and citation analysis of Publications in Science & Technology in FUO

S/N	Faculty	Department	Number of FUO staff in S & T	Number of Publications	Number of Citations/Impact
	Engineering	Chemical Engineering	5	184	2,717
		Civil Engineering	7	104	274
		Elect/Electronics	6	117	594
		Mechanical Engineering	5	53	226
		Pet and Gas	6	58	259
		Mechatronics	1	1	1
	Science	Biology	7	124	902

		Biochemistry	5	170	1,165
		Chemistry	18	500	5,649
		Computer Science	7	65	71
		Microbiology	11	321	2,637
		Mathematics & Statistics	7	169	853
	Education	Science Education	6	48	94
		Library and Information Science	11	210	2,371
		Total	102	2,124	17,813

Source. (Etim et al., 2023)

Figure 2: Graphic representation of relationship between number of publications and citations/ impact

Source: Research Data

Department	Sum	Average	Variance		
Chemical Engineering	2901	1450.5	3208044.5		
Civil Engineering	378	189	14450		
Elect/Electronics	711	355.5	113764.5		
Mechanical Engineering	279	139.5	14964.5		

Pet and Gas	317	158.5	20200.5		
Mechatronics	2	1	0		
Biology	1026	513	302642		
Biochemistry	1335	667.5	495012.5		
Chemistry	6149	3074.5	13256100.5		
Computer Science	136	68	18		
Microbiology	2958	1479	2681928		
Mathematics & Statistics	1022	511	233928		
Science Education	142	71	1058		
Library and Information Science	2581	1290.5	2334960.5		
Number of Publications	2124	151.7142857	16830.83516		
Number of Citations/Impact	17813	1272.357143	2512506.709		
ANOVA					
Source of Variation	df	MS	F	p-value	F-crit
Rows	13	1461169.19	1.367920313	0.290151256	2.576927085
Columns	1	8790882.893	8.229866441	0.013174053	4.667192714
Error	13	1068168.354			
Total	27				

Source: Research Data

Table 4 depicts that there is significant relationship between the number of publications and the number of citations /impact because the p-value of 0.013174053 is far less than the significant level of 0.05 and the F-value of 8.229866441 is greater than the F-critical of 4.667192714.

Table 5: Number of FUO Respondents in S & T and Number of Citations/Impact Result

Department	Sum	Average	Variance		
Chemical Engineering	2722	1361	3677472		
Civil Engineering	281	140.5	35644.5		
Elect/Electronics	600	300	172872		

Mechanical Engineering	231	115.5	24420.5		
Pet and Gas	265	132.5	32004.5		
Mechatronics	2	1	0		
Biology	909	454.5	400512.5		
Biochemistry	1170	585	672800		
Chemistry	5667	2833.5	15854080.5		
Computer Science	78	39	2048		
Microbiology	2648	1324	3447938		
Mathematics & Statistics	860	430	357858		
Science Education	100	50	3872		
Library and Information Science	2382	1191	2784800		
Number of FUO Respondents in S & T	102	7.285714286	15.6043956		
Number of Citations/Impact	17813	1272.357143	2512506.709		
ANOVA					
Source of Variation	df	MS	F	p-value	F-crit
Rows	13	1261485.201	1.008351541	0.494132525	2.576927085
Columns	1	11202840.04	8.954842284	0.010388347	4.667192714
Error	13	1251037.113			
Total	27				

Source: Research Data

Table 5 There is significant relationship between the number of respondents in S & T, and the number of citations/impact because the analysis revealed a p-value of 0.010388347 much less than the significant level of 0.05 and the F-value of 8.954842284 is larger than F-critical of 4.667192714.

Impact of Science & Technology Research at Federal University Otuoke Community

According to the research data, the Department of Chemistry had the largest number of publications (500) and research impact with citation count of five thousand six hundred and forty-nine (5,649) of all science and technology programmes at the Federal University of Otuoke, a clear lead depicting a high research production plus an over 5,000 citation counts accruing, indicating an unrivalled impact. Their study has had an impact on in-country technology development (indigenous technology) in remediation, agriculture, and entrepreneurship. The following is a summary of the areas of impact. On closer inspection, the department's impact extends across the university community, department's students, and the Niger Delta Area, particularly in the following important areas: in-country technology development (indigenous technology) in the following specific areas: Remediation of petroleum-impacted habitats in the Niger Delta region; Increasing the value of oil-polluted farmlands by the domestication of more than 20 non-indigenous (foreign) crops; Chemistry food-based entrepreneurship aimed at the department's students, such as 'Garri', palm oil, and so on; Chemistry non-food-based entrepreneurship aimed at empowering students with the department's significant success in the area of paint manufacture; A fully equipped ecological garden supplied to the university community by partners.

The Department of Chemical Engineering had the second largest impact (2,717) while ranking fifth in publication output (184). This is most likely due to the fact that these researchers created a template for analysing the trending effects and hazards of oil leakage to public health in relation to the quality of home water, which made up for the seemingly inferior number of publications. They also created an efficient bioremediation approach for crude oil-contaminated swampy soil. Locally generated BioMass has been used to cleanse wastewater, notably industrial effluent and crude oil-polluted bodies of water. From locally available biomass, the Chemical Engineering research team was able to manufacture high-quality biodiesel, biogas, and activated carbon--from waste to riches.

The Department of Microbiology with research output (321), impact (2637) has established the bioremediation capabilities of microbes in non-crude oil-related land pollution in abattoirs within Bayelsa state. Medicinal plant extracts and the synergistic effects of the different medicinal plants obtained within the university community have been tested and found to be effective against many pathogenic organisms causing potent diseases in the Niger Delta region. Assessment of the bacterial load of many ready-to-eat foods within the Federal University Otuoke community was found to be high in pathogenic organisms. Relevant authorities have been advised accordingly to avert the breakdown of foodborne diseases. They have identified resistant strains of pathogenic bacteria responsible for antimicrobial resistance within the university community and clinical settings within the state. Using basic Microbiological techniques our study identified *E. coli*, *S. epidermis*, *Enterobacter spp*, *Shigella spp*, *Proteus spp* and *Salmonella*

Paratyphi A from processed freshwater clam (*Galatea paradoxa*) from food vendors within the university community. These bacteria are potential pathogens associated with diarrhoea, enteric fever and skin infections. Bacterial species such as *E. coli*, *Salmonella* species, *P. mirabilis* have been identified in surface waters in the coastal communities within Wilberforce Island in Bayelsa State, this indicated that these water bodies are highly polluted and is not safe for use by the communities that resort to it as their means of water supply. The presence of potential enteric pathogens such as *E. coli*, *Proteus* spp, *Shigella* spp, and *Salmonella typhi* has been seen among apparently healthy students of Microbiology, these bacteria isolated also showed antibiotic-resistant strains, hence this could be a result of indiscriminate use of antibiotics and asymptomatic carriers of potential pathogens. The students have been fully educated and exposed to the potential threat of the abuse of antibiotics. Revealing the growing trend of multidrug resistance among commercially available antibiotics utilized in the management of diarrhoea which can cause an increase in morbidity and mortality associated with acute diarrhoea. An assessment of some commercially sold toothpaste was carried out and its potential effectiveness in preventing oral diseases among students and the general public health has been established. Food products and waste materials with the help of microorganisms resulted in the production of bioethanol and other substances, targeted at developing entrepreneurship skills for Microbiology students.

The University Library is one of the research hubs at Federal University Otuoke, with publications output (210) and impact (2,371). As a contribution to the university community, the university library organizes conferences, workshops and training for both teaching and non-teaching staff have gone a long way to enhance the job performances of staff in their respective duties. The establishment of a bookshop, where stationaries and lecturers' written books are made to be deposited and sold is directly or indirectly growing the internally generated revenue of the institution. Bindery and reprographic sections are made to function optimally. Students are now made to print and bound their projects in the bindery section of the library of the institution. This also has improved the fee-based sources of IGR of the institution and creates jobs for the university community. The Information literacy laboratory houses an in-house database developed for use by students in the absence of Internet connectivity and other subscribed electronic resources. Registered students and staff are given password access to some of these databases. This has enhanced the academic performance and overall productivity of staff and students in the university community as a whole.

The Department of Biochemistry came fifth in impact assessment with a publication output of (170) and a citation impact (1,165). Taking advantage of wide medicinal plant species in Bayelsa State, they have formulated an indigenous plant-based therapies and worthy of note as the arthritis remedy. From our research output especially in the area of phytomedicine, we have been able to establish scientifically and document the efficacy of many indigenous medicinal plants used in folklore medical practice.

Conclusion

There are various effects of globalization on society. The presence of science and technology ought to spur growth in the neighbourhood. A crucial component of economic growth and development is the capacity to generate new scientific and technological information and transfer it into new goods or procedures. However, there needs to be more research done and technology capabilities need to be improved. Technology is made possible by a mix of information, approaches, resources, and abilities. The clarity needed for technological growth can be found in these four components. In order to assure the effective application of plentiful resources for industrialisation, we must ensure adequate growth of the human resource in science and technology. Government funding for science and technology research should be a primary priority.

Acknowledgement

The authors of the research wish to acknowledge the funding received from **Tertiary Education Fund (TetFund)** Abuja through the Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State, Nigeria without which the work would not have seen the light of day.

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